

Original paper

MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI O'SPIRINLARNING EMOTSIONAL MUNOSABATLARIDA O'ZIGA XOS IJTIMOY-PSIXIK XUSUSIYATLAR

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Annotatsiya

KIRISH: o'smirlik - bu shaxsning ijtimoiy, shaxsiy va ma'naviy-amaliy o'zini o'zi belgilashining boshlanishi davri. O'rta maktab o'quvchilarining hissiy va emotsional rivojlanishi masalasi murakkab va talabchan masalalardan biridir. Mustaqil hayotga tayyorgarlik o'smirlik davridan boshlanadi, insonning qadriyatlar tizimi, dunyoqarashi, kasb tanlashi va fuqarolik ahamiyatini tasdiqlashning shakllanishi sodir bo'ladi. Natijada, ana shu ijtimoiy va shaxsiy omillar ta'sirida o'spirin va uning atrofidagi odamlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarning butun tizimi qayta tuziladi, uning o'ziga bo'lgan munosabati o'zgaradi. Ushbu maqolada maktab yoshidagi o'spirinlarining emotsional munosabatlarida o'ziga xos ijtimoiy-psixik xususiyatlar tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, o'smirlar o'rtasidagi ijtimoiy munosabatlarning psixologik xususiyatlari qator ilmiy manbalar asosida ko'rib chiqiladi.

MAQSAD: tadqiqotning maqsadi, maktab yoshidagi o'spirinlarining emotsional munosabatlarining ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlarini empirik tadqiq etish hamda shaxsiy rivojlanishiga, ularning o'zini anglash jarayoniga psixologik-pedagogik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: MDH mamlakatlari miqyosida yuqori sinf o'quvchilari hisoblangan o'spirinlarning emotsional munosabatlarining ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari doir tadqiqotlar A.G. Gretsov, Y.N. Vasileva, N.A. Bogoslovskaya, V.N. Nosulenko, I.V. Starikova L.S. Vigotskiy, L.I. Bojovich, M.I. Lisina, I.S. Kon, A.V. Mudrik, L.M. Fridman, I.Yu. Kulagina, N.D. Levitov, L.D. Stolyarenko ilmiy ishlarida keng urg'u berilgan va atroflicha tadqiq etilgan.

Mamlakatimizning pedagog olimlaridan o'smir yoshdagi bolalarning emotsional munosabatlarining ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlariga doir tadqiqotlarni T.R. Bekmirov, Z.T. Nishonova, G.K. Alimova, M. Radjabova, A.K. Shamsheva va boshqalar olib borganlar. Tadqiqotimiz davomida ilmiy bilishning kuzatish, so'rovnoma, analiz va sintez, mantiqiylik usullaridan foydalangan holda mavzuni yoritishga harakat qilindi.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: shaxsning axloqiy jihatdan intensiv tarkib topishi, xatti-harakatlarining axloqiy etnik normalarini o'zlashtirish o'smirlik yoshining eng muhim psixologik karakteristikalaridan biri hisblanadi. O'smirlik yoshida faqat jismoniy taraqqiyot yuzaga kelmay, balki bolaning shaxsi ham sezilarli rivojlanadi. Bola shaxsining

rivojlanishi tevarak-atrofdagi voqelikning ta'siri ortida maktabdagi, ta'lim tarbiya jarayoni ta'sirida, kollektiv va tarbiyachilarning g'oyaviy rahbarligi ostida amalga oshadi.

O'smirlik yoshi xatti-harakatlarida suyana boshlaydigan dunyoqarashlarning, ma'naviy e'tiqod, prinsip qoida, idealarining, baxolash mulohazalari sistemasining tarkib topishi davridir. Agar kichik maktab yoshidalik davrida u yoki kattalarning, ya'ni o'qituvchilar va ota-onalarning bevosita ko'rsatmalari bilan, yoki o'zining tasodifiy va impulsiv istaklari ta'siri bilan harakat qilgan bo'lsa, endilikda uning uchun o'z xatti-harakatlarining prinsipi, o'zining qarashlari va e'tiqodlari asosiy ahamiyat kasb etadi. O'qituvchi va tarbiyachi shuni nazarda tutishi lozimki, xuddi ana shu yoshda axloqiy ong taraqqiyotiga zamin qo'yiladi.

XULOSA: shaxsning erta o'spirinlikdagi eng muhim hislatlaridan biri o'z-o'zini hurmatlash, o'z-o'ziga baho berish hamda o'zini shaxs deb tan olish yoki olmaslik darajasidir. O'spirinlar o'zlarida shaxsning muayyan kompleks sifatlarini hosil qilishga intiladilar. O'z-o'zini tarbiyalash masalalarida bir butun ma'naviy psixologik qiyofani shakllantirish masalasi qiziqtiradi. Bunda shaxs ideal va namunaning mavjudligi katta ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'smirlik, jismoniy rivojlanish, impulsiv istaklar, qat'iyat, o'z-o'zini anglash, xarakter, ijtimoiy hayot, kollektivizm.

Iqtibos uchun: Xalilova M.N. maktab yoshidagi o'spirinlarning emotsional munosabatlarida o'ziga xos ijtimoiy-psixik xususiyatlar // Inter education & global study. 2025. №4. B.628-636.

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ ПОДРОСТКОВ ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: подростковый возраст — период начала социального, личностного и духовно-практического самоопределения человека. Проблема сенсорного и эмоционального развития учащихся старших классов является одной из самых сложных и ответственных. Подготовка к самостоятельной жизни начинается в подростковом возрасте, когда формируется система ценностей человека, мировоззрение, выбор карьеры, утверждение важности гражданства. В результате под влиянием этих социальных и личностных факторов перестраивается вся система взаимоотношений подростка с окружающими его людьми, меняется его отношение к себе. В статье анализируются социально-психологические особенности эмоциональных отношений подростков школьного возраста. На основе ряда научных источников также рассматриваются психологические особенности социальных взаимоотношений подростков.

ЦЕЛЬ: целью исследования является эмпирическое изучение социально-психологических особенностей эмоциональных отношений подростков школьного возраста и разработка психолого-педагогических рекомендаций по их личностному развитию и процессу самосознания.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: исследования социально-психологических особенностей эмоциональных отношений подростков-старшекласников стран СНГ проводились А.Г. Грецовым, Ю.Н. Васильева, Н.А. Богословская, В.Н. Носуленко, И.В. Старикова Л.С. Выготский, Л.И. Бойович, М.И. Лисина, И.С. Кон, А.В. Мудрик, Л.М. Фридман, И.Ю. Кулагина, Н.Д. Левитов, Л.Д. Научная деятельность Столяренко широко освещалась и подробно исследовалась.

Среди отечественных ученых-педагогов Т.Р. проведены исследования социально-психологических особенностей эмоциональных отношений подростков. Бекмиров, З.Т. Нишонова, Г.К. Алимova, М. Раджабова, А.К. Шамшeтова и другие.

В ходе нашего исследования мы попытались пролить свет на эту тему, используя научные методы наблюдения, анкетирования, анализа и синтеза, а также логики.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: интенсивное нравственное формирование личности, усвоение этических и этнических норм поведения считается одной из важнейших психологических особенностей подросткового возраста. В подростковом возрасте происходит не только физическое развитие, но и существенное развитие личности ребенка. Развитие личности ребенка происходит под воздействием окружающей действительности, под влиянием учебно-воспитательного процесса в школе, под идейным руководством коллектива и воспитателей.

Подростковый возраст — это период формирования мировоззрения, духовных убеждений, принципов, идей и систем оценок, которые начинают определять поведение. Если в ранние школьные годы он действовал либо по непосредственным указаниям взрослых, то есть учителей и родителей, либо под влиянием собственных случайных и импульсивных желаний, то теперь для него первостепенное значение имеют принципы его собственного поведения, его собственные взгляды и убеждения. Педагогам и воспитателям следует помнить, что именно в этом возрасте закладывается основа развития нравственного сознания.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: одной из важнейших характеристик человека в раннем подростковом возрасте является уровень его самооценки, самоуважения и осознание им себя как личности. Подростки стремятся развить в себе определенные сложные черты личности. В вопросах самообразования интерес представляет вопрос формирования целостного духовно-психологического облика. При этом большое значение имеет наличие идеала и образца для подражания.

Ключевые слова: подростковый возраст, физическое развитие, импульсивные желания, целеустремленность, самосознание, характер, социальная жизнь, коллективизм.

Для цитирования: М.Н.Халилова Социально-психологические особенности эмоциональных отношений подростков школьного возраста // Inter education & global study. 2025. №4. В. 628-636.

SPECIFIC SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES IN THE EMOTIONAL RELATIONSHIPS OF SCHOOL-AGE ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation

INTRODUCTION. Adolescence is the period of the beginning of a person's social, personal, spiritual, and practical self-determination. The emotional and mental development of high school students is one of the most complex and demanding issues. Preparation for independent life begins in adolescence, the formation of a person's value system, worldview, choice of profession, and affirmation of the importance of citizenship takes place. As a result, under the influence of these social and personal factors, the entire system of relationships between a teenager and the people around him is restructured, and his attitude towards himself changes. This article analyzes the specific socio-psychological features of the emotional relationships of school-age adolescents. Also, the psychological features of social relationships between adolescents are considered based on several scientific sources.

AIM. the purpose of the study is to empirically investigate the socio-psychological characteristics of the emotional relationships of school-age adolescents and to develop psychological and pedagogical recommendations for their personal development and the process of self-awareness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. research on socio-psychological characteristics of emotional relationships of high school students in the CIS countries A.G. Gretsov, Y.N. Vasileva, N.A. Bogoslovskaya, V.N. Nosulenko, I.V. Starikova L.S. Vygotsky, L.I. Bojovich, M.I. Lisina, I.S. Kohn, A.V. Mudrik, L.M. Friedman, I. Yu. Kulagina, N.D. Levitov, L.D. Stolyarenko's scientific works were widely emphasized and thoroughly researched.

Among the pedagogic-psychological scientists of Uzbekistan, T.R. Bekmirov, Z.T. Nishonova, G.K. Alimova, M. Radjabova, A.K. Shamshetova and others.

During our research, we attempted to shed light on the topic using scientific methods of observation, questionnaire, analysis and synthesis, and logic.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. the intensive formation of a person's moral character and the assimilation of ethical and ethnic norms of behavior is considered one of the most important psychological characteristics of adolescence. In adolescence, not

only physical development occurs, but also the child's personality develops significantly. The development of a child's personality takes place under the influence of the surrounding reality, under the influence of the educational process, at school, and under the ideological guidance of the collective and educators.

Adolescence is a period of formation of a system of worldviews, spiritual beliefs, principles, rules, ideas, and evaluation judgments that begin to be based on behavior. If in junior school age, he acted either under the direct instructions of adults, that is, teachers and parents, or under the influence of his own random and impulsive desires, now the principle of his behavior, his views and beliefs become of primary importance for him. Teachers and educators should keep in mind that it is at this age that the foundation for the development of moral consciousness is laid.

CONCLUSION. One of the most important characteristics of a person in early adolescence is the level of self-esteem, self-assessment and recognition or not of oneself as a person. Adolescents strive to form certain complex qualities of a person in themselves. In matters of self-education, the issue of forming a holistic spiritual and psychological image is of interest. In this regard, the presence of an ideal and role model for a person is of great importance.

Key words: Adolescence, physical development, impulsive desires, determination, self-awareness, character, social life, collectivism.

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Adolescence is the period of the beginning of a person's social, personal and spiritual-practical self-determination. The problem of emotional and emotional development of high school students is one of the complex and demanding issues. Preparation for an independent life begins in adolescence, the formation of a value system, worldview, career choice and confirmation of a person's civic importance takes place. As a result, under the influence of these social and personal factors, the entire system of relations between the high school student and the people around him is restructured, and his attitude towards himself changes. Relationships and related communication are an integral and very important component of young people's lives. In this, their personality, emotional and behavioral management sphere and activity characteristics are formed and polished. With adults and peers, a complex system of relationships and relationships, often full of excessive emotional tension, appears. It is in mutual relations and communication that purely human needs are satisfied, which are very important for the formation of a well-rounded, emotionally stable person. Young people should perceive and evaluate their problems and feelings not from the perspective of adults, but from the perspective of the importance of boys and girls to

them. Because the adequate development and stability of the emotional sphere in adolescents is important for entering into interpersonal relations and socialization.

T.R. Bekmirov's educational and methodological guide, it was prepared on the topic of using innovative educational technologies in teaching the topic "Emotional volitional states of the individual", which is considered the main topic of the "Psychology and pedagogy" module. In the first chapters of the educational manual, in the module of psychology and pedagogy, issues such as the main aspects of the emotional volitional states of a person and the use of innovative educational technologies in effective teaching are put forward. In the next chapters of the educational manual, methods of covering the topic using several types of innovative educational technologies and interactive educational methods introduced into the educational process are shown. A presentation suitable for the subject, glossaries, appendices, and a subject syllabus is provided [1]. Z.T. "Psychology of development" of the team of authors headed by Nishonova. The textbook "Pedagogical psychology" talks about the subject, methods, departments of developmental and pedagogical psychology, education, training, and teacher psychology. It reflects the characteristics of the psychological development of a person from infancy to old age. The chapter on educational psychology describes the psychological nature of educational activities, psychological components of knowledge acquisition, non-traditional methods of education, development of independent thinking, and management of the educational process. In the chapter on educational psychology, psychological mechanisms that increase the effectiveness of education, in the chapter on teacher psychology, pedagogic skills, and requirements for the teacher are discussed [2].

Based on the above research, in our article, we want to think about the socio-psychological characteristics of emotional relationships of high school students.

The development of the morally intensive formation of a person, and the assimilation of ethical ethnic norms of behavior are important psychological characteristics of adolescence.

In adolescence, not only physical development occurs, but also the child's personality develops significantly. The development of the child's personality is carried out under the influence of the surrounding reality at school, under the influence of the educational process, and the ideological leadership of the collective and educators.

Adolescence is a period of formation of worldviews, moral beliefs, principles, ideas, and a system of evaluations, which are based on behavior. If during the period of junior school age, he acted either under the direct instructions of adults, that is, teachers and parents, or under the influence of his own random and impulsive desires, now for him his behavior - the principle of actions, one's views and beliefs are of primary importance. The teacher and educator should take into account that at this age, the foundation for the development of moral consciousness is laid.

High school students differentiate different things. If he breaks a chair while playing during recess and needs to be fixed in the workshop, this is not a punishment. It is not a

punishment if he is forced to sweep the place he made dirty. The logic of this is clear for a teenager: it is not punishment, but correction of the results of his actions.

Psychologists set themselves the task of studying the content of the spiritual consciousness of teenagers, their moral concepts, and their imagination. Studies show that teenagers generally have a high level of spiritual consciousness. The majority of teenagers correctly understand the spiritual concepts appropriate for young people. Here are some examples. Determination - "It is a characteristic that when a person starts to do the most difficult things, he carries it to the end without fearing any failure." and serves good deeds. (12 years old) By the end of adolescence, the level of deep understanding will increase significantly. "Humility is being able to judge oneself rationally, to be critical of oneself and one's actions." [3;21]

The moral ideals of teenagers begin to emerge as they are closely connected with the formation of faith and worldview. These ideals are sufficiently deep, meaningful, and active, and these ideals serve as a kind of moral standard, and the teenager equates his behavior with this standard. For young teenagers, a specific person is usually ideal. This person embodies the qualities that a teenager highly values.

Many such ideals are parents, teachers, or characters in favorite books and movies. In older adolescents, generalized images, which are a set of ideals, begin to emerge as ideals. Teenagers plan their future life and activities in their dreams. Big jobs and heroic professions, people of science, and cocktails surround the minds of our teenagers. This is related to the wide and deep social events in the life of our country and the real heroic deeds of the present time. In recent years, teenagers' dreams and hopes for heroism have increasingly focused their lives on conquering outer space, and rocket technology, using new types of energy, and conducting scientific research in the fields of chemistry, physics, biology, and medicine. connecting. The dreams of our teenagers indicate their desire to participate in the life of our country and socially useful activities. They closely connect their future lives, their place in the life of our country with the lives of other Soviet people [4; 224].

In the poem written by K. Vera, a student of the seventh grade, the feeling of internationalism, friendship, the desire to act, the feeling of actively helping the people fighting for freedom, and the feeling of actively helping the people fighting for freedom were vividly demonstrated [3;22].

Kindness is a characteristic of weak and weak-willed people, a real (brave) person should be lazy, careless, persistent, rude, and sharp. Adolescent boys are inclined to show courage and be leaders. This sometimes even leads to serious violations of discipline. They say: "Courage" or boldness is the act of risking one's life, regardless of the reason, one's commitment to the most dangerous work. The most important thing is not to see. No one needs courage, but courage anyway. Foolish courage is better than wise cowardice.

In one of the schools, teenagers invented such an exercise: they jumped from the balcony of the fourth floor to the balcony of the third floor. hanging by the hand, swaying

to one side or the other, and then jumping. To find out why they did this, the director called these children to his office. At first, the children were silent, thinking that they would fight, but after a while, they became bolder and began to say that what they had done was an "examination for the certificate of bravery": Whoever did this, was brave, and whoever did not, he was the heart. The director, who has experienced many unpleasant moments, says to the children: "If we say this, how would it seem to you, whoever did this, he is stupid, and if whoever did not, he is smart." The children replied: "Whatever we say, it's better to think of me as a fool than a coward."

It is important to understand that during adolescence, when a person is forming as a person, he feels like an adult and that adults can resist their will. One of the older teenagers proudly says: "I am a principled person, I have never apologized to anyone in my life!" All this consists of a unique moral worldview! After psychologists got acquainted with the characteristics of adolescents (the opinions of adolescents were given above), it became clear that the characteristics of adolescents are fully consistent with their behavior, that is, their moral consciousness is related to their behavior. "grows" to the level of his actions, determines his actions. Recently, L.N. Desev researched the content of moral concepts of teenagers (under the leadership of A.G. Kovalov) and showed that their understanding of moral categories is often superficial and formal.

The need for self-realization arises from the needs of life and practical activities. Self-awareness is determined by the growing needs of adults and the collective. In connection with the development of interest in social life and the collective, teenagers should evaluate their capabilities, determine their place in the collective, and respond to the demands placed on them at a high level by their behavior and personality traits. there is an urge to understand whether it helps or hinders. The development of self-awareness in teenagers begins with their awareness of their behavior. In the beginning, the self-awareness of adolescents is based on the opinions of other people, adults (teachers, parents), collective, and friends. A young teenager looks at himself as if through the eyes of the people around him. As age increases, the tendency to independently analyze and evaluate one's personality begins. Finally, complex synthetic qualities (sense of duty, sense of dignity and conscience, principledness) representing the multifaceted relations of a person are understood. This consistency in the understanding of the ever-expanding qualities of a person is known and can be easily explained.

So, as shown above, one of the most important characteristics of a person in early adolescence is self-esteem, self-evaluation, and the level of recognizing oneself as a person or not. Adolescents strive to form certain complex qualities of a person. In matters of self-education, the issue of forming a whole spiritual psychological image is of interest. In this case, the existence of an ideal and role model is very important. For example: if boys consider the characters in the movie to be ideal for them; Our daughters are hardworking women, attractive public figures, graceful housewives, or teenagers who cannot solve the complex problems of determining their status. This issue can be solved with the participation of parents, peers, and teachers, taking into account their support.

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